

Electroanalysis of Cobalt in Industrial Effluents

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Of late, trace metal analysis in industrial effluents has assumed importance as waste water is an efficient pathway for toxic metal pollution of the aquatic environment. Cobalt is one of the element of concern in this context because of its wide applications in industries as metal catalyst. It was thus of interest to develop a rapid sensitive method for its determination in industrial effluents. The present communication describes a differential pulse polarographic (DPP) method for the determination of cobalt in continuation of the author's work on trace metal analysis. Similar studies related to chromium¹, iron² and nickel³ have been reported elsewhere.

Nadkarni⁴ determined cobalt and other elements in fly ash and coal by inductively coupled plasma spectroscopy. King and James⁵ analysed electroplating waste for Co, Cu, Hg and Ni using HPLC. In manganese sulphate electrolyte, Ni and Co were determined employing DPP by Adeloju and Tran⁶. The authors have employed DPP in combination with dc-polarography to develop conditions in which cobalt could be determined in presence of Cr, Pb and Cd. Effluent samples of Jodhpur industrial area were analysed for their cobalt contents.

Results and Discussion

In ammonium citrate buffer, cobalt (1×10^{-3} M) yielded a dc-polarographic wave whose half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) was found to be pH-dependent. At pH 9.5, a single reduction wave was observed with a $E_{1/2}$ of -1.36 V which appeared to be diffusion-controlled. This wave was chosen for detailed studies and was made the basis for the determination of cobalt by DPP.

The nature of the electrode process was investigated by performing CV at HMDE in the potential range of -1.0 to -1.6 V where it showed a lone cathodic peak (E_{pc}) = -1.27 V at scan rate 60 mV s^{-1} with no corresponding anodic peak, illustrating irreversible process (Fig. 1) under the experimental conditions.

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of Co^{II} in ammonium citrate buffer; $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} = 1 \times 10^{-4}$ M, pH = 9.5, scan rate = 60 mV s^{-1} .

Cobalt showed a DP peak in citrate buffer and it was also observed that at pH 9.5, cobalt could be determined in the presence of chromium, lead and cadmium because of their different peak potentials; Cr^{VI} , -0.35 V; Pb^{II} , -0.61 V; Cd^{II} , -0.83 V and Co^{II} , -1.36 V. A DP polarogram of solution containing Cr^{VI} , Pb^{II} , Cd^{II} and Co^{II} is shown in Fig. 2. The peak height of cobalt was found to be proportional to its concentration in the range 0.01–12.3 ppm. Standard deviation values (\pm) of 2.76 and 4.45 were observed for the determination of cobalt in synthetic and industrial effluent respectively. The detection limit approached 0.01 ppm.

Fig. 2. DPP of solution containing $1 \times 10^{-5} M$ Cr^{VI} , $3 \times 10^{-5} M$ Pb^{II} , $2 \times 10^{-5} M$ Cd^{II} and $4 \times 10^{-5} M$ Co^{II} ions in the presence of ammonium citrate buffer (pH = 9.5); scan rate = $5 mV s^{-1}$, modulation amplitude = 50 mV, pulse duration = 57 ms, clock time of pulse = 1 s.

Applications : The treated effluent sample was taken in the polarographic cell and its pH was adjusted to 9.5 by adding citrate buffer. The DP polarograms were recorded in the potential range of -1.1 to -1.6 V. The quantitation was made by standard addition method⁷ for which peak currents were measured at -1.36 V after making blank corrections. Results obtained from 27 samples showed a minimum amount of 0.015 ppm cobalt and a maximum amount of 0.022 ppm with an average of 0.018 ppm. Atomic absorption spectroscopic method was employed to compare the results obtained by DPP. A comparative listing has been made in Table 1.

Experimental

174-A polarographic analyser alongwith a drop timer and x-y recorder was used to record dc and DP polarograms. Potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (SCE). Cyclic

voltammograms were drawn with a CV-27 (BAS) cyclic voltammograph in which a hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) was used as the working electrode and Ag/AgCl as the reference electrode. A platinum wire was employed as the auxiliary electrode in all the experiments. The solutions were deaerated by bubbling purified nitrogen for 20 min prior to each experiment.

TABLE 1—CONCENTRATION OF COBALT IN INDUSTRIAL EFFLUENTS DETERMINED BY DPP AND AAS

Sample no.	Concn. of Co (ppm)	
	DPP	AAS
1	0.022	0.020
2	0.018	0.015
3	0.016	0.015
4	0.015	0.017
Average	0.018	0.017

Industrial effluent samples were collected from different parts of Basni industrial area of Jodhpur and these were filtered to remove suspended particulates. A 250 ml of sample was digested with an oxidising mixture of $HNO_3-H_2SO_4$ (10 : 1, v/v) and evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in buffer solution (25 ml).

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References

1. P. SHARMA and R. C. KAPOOR, *Int. J. Environ. Anal. Chem.*, 1987, **30**, 51.
2. R. C. KAPOOR, K. C. K. MATHUR and P. SHARMA, *Int. J. Environ. Anal. Chem.*, 1984, **17**, 223.
3. P. SHARMA, S. KUMBHAT and C. RAWAT, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 195.
4. R. A. NADKARNI, *Anal. Chem.*, 1980, **52**, 929.
5. J. N. KING and S. F. JAMES, *Anal. Chem.*, 1987, **59**, 703.
6. S. B. ADELOJU and T. TRAN, *Anal. Lett.*, 1986, **19**, 1633.
7. H. WILLARD, L. MERRIT and J. DEAN, "Instrumental Methods of Analysis", 5th. ed., Van Nostrand, New York, 1974.